
PROFESSIONAL STABILITY OF A FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHER IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract.

Professional self-development of a teacher's personality is the key to his professional career, so professional development and improvement today becomes a priority for every teacher. The article deals with the main aspects of the professional stability of a foreign language teacher in higher education.

Keywords.

professional competence, skills, professional stability, pedagogical training, teacher.

Introduction:

The teaching profession, as already noted, is both transformative and managerial. In addition, in order to manage the process of personal development, you need to be competent. The concept of professional competence of a teacher therefore expresses the unity of his theoretical and practical readiness in the integral structure of the personality and characterizes his professionalism. The content of the specialist's professional competence is determined by the qualification characteristic. It is a normative model of the teacher's competence, reflecting the scientifically based composition of professional knowledge, skills and abilities. A qualification characteristic is, in essence, a set of generalized requirements for a teacher at the level of his theoretical and practical experience.

Main part:

The content of pedagogical education as a whole can be considered, therefore, as a unity of knowledge and skills, the experience of creative activity and the experience of an emotional and value attitude to pedagogical reality. The relationship of these components does not contradict their linearity, when the previous elements can, to a certain extent, exist separately from the subsequent ones, but the subsequent ones are impossible without the previous ones. Conditionally separating professional competence from other personal formations,

we mean that the assimilation of knowledge, the accumulation of professional skills is a necessary condition for the acquisition of certain professional skills, which is the main component of professional stability [1, 3].

Reflecting the unity of the content and national structures of pedagogical activity, the psychological preparation of the future teacher presupposes a fairly broad knowledge of the methodological foundations of pedagogy; patterns of socialization and personality development; essence, goals and technologies of education and training; patterns of age-related anatomical, physiological and mental development of student youth. Therefore, the psychological and pedagogical training of the future teacher, as a first approximation, models and implements the methodology, theory and technology of pedagogical sustainability, lays the foundations for the humanistically oriented thinking of the teacher.

Psychological-pedagogical and special knowledge is a necessary but not sufficient condition for professional competence. Many of them, in particular theoretical, practical and methodological knowledge, are a necessary condition for pedagogical skills and abilities.

Pedagogical mastery is a set of pedagogical actions consistently deployed in the external or internal plan, some of which can be automated, aimed at solving the problems of forming a harmonious personality and based on relevant theoretical knowledge. Such an understanding of the essence of pedagogical skill has a direct exit into the practice of training specialists [3,131]. This determines the leading role of theoretical knowledge in the formation of the practical readiness of future specialists, as well as the unity of the theoretical and practical training of the future teacher, and is also aimed at developing the ability to think and act in unity. Pedagogically, it manifests itself as a system of ideal and a system of objective actions, respectively.

Professional training of specialists has a multi-level character of pedagogical skill from reproductive to creative. Professional readiness implies that a specialist has an appropriate level of formation and development of qualities necessary for successful professional activity, the presence of an appropriate level of personal physical culture. This is obvious, since any professional activity assumes that one or another level of a person's application of physical forces, physical energy is associated with the expenditure of not only mental, but also physical energy.

The leading and most difficult side of the specialist's professional readiness is the psychological and professional readiness of the specialist's psyche.

This is one or another degree of preparedness and mood of the psyche, spiritual forces of a specialist for solving professional problems, developing

professional stability of a specialist. It should be noted that the personality of a specialist teacher develops and forms in the system of social relations, depending on the conditions (spiritual and material) of his life and work, but, above all, in the process of pedagogical activity. and pedagogical communication, and each of the areas The work of a teacher makes special demands on his personal qualities [21,18].

Indicators of the maturity of pedagogical activity, in our opinion, is the formation of its components: for example, in the course of setting pedagogical tasks by the teacher, their hierarchization by degree of importance, restructuring in the lesson, pedagogical goal setting, pedagogical goal setting is formed:

- Mastering the system of means and methods for solving pedagogical problems by the teacher, the ability to penetrate into the essence of phenomena forms his pedagogical thinking;
- Introspection develops his pedagogical reflection;
- In the process of organizing optimal pedagogical communication, a pedagogical tact is formed; the teacher's personality is characterized by a pedagogical orientation - a stable dominant system of motives, therefore, professional stability is being formed.

The presented understanding of the essence of pedagogical skills allows us to understand their internal structure, i.e. interdependent connection of actions, components of skills as relatively independent private skills¹⁸. This, in turn, opens up opportunities both for combining a multitude of pedagogical skills for various reasons, and for their conditional decomposition in practical fields. For example, the ability to “hold a conversation” can be decomposed into particular skills:

To determine a topic that most adequately reflects the interests and needs of students and at the same time takes into account the leading educational tasks facing the audience

Select content, select forms, methods and means of education, taking into account the age of pupils and specific conditions, etc.

Changes and transformations in any sphere of human activity must begin with a change and transformation of its subject, its creator [23,912].

There is a philosophical principle - like is created by as the morality of students is formed by the morality of the teacher, knowledge - by knowledge, skill - by skill. No modern teaching technologies and technical means will help the

¹⁸ Baidenko V.I., Oskarson B. Basic skills (key competences) as an integrating factor of educational process // Professional education and formation of personality of a specialist: scientific-methodical collection. - M., 2002.

teacher to build his pedagogical activity if he himself is personally and professionally not ready for it. Determining the requirements for the personality of the teacher, ensuring his readiness for professional activity, psychological and pedagogical science seeks to combine them into more generalized integral properties. First, they include professionalism as a set of personal characteristics of a person necessary for the successful implementation of pedagogical activity, which reflects the unity of the theoretical and practical readiness of the teacher to carry out activities, and in modern conditions is directly connected with professional stability [50, 1415].

Professionalism is a concept that occupies one of the first places in the scale of modern values. The essence of the social reason is that the transition to market relations brought with it competition in the labor market and, as a result, increased requirements for a specialist. If in the recent past getting a job was guaranteed by a diploma, today the employer is primarily interested in competence, creativity, intellectual skills, the ability to make decisions and be responsible for their implementation, i.e. professional stability of a specialist [18,3521]. The essence of a personal reason is that there is an opportunity to reveal one's abilities, to satisfy individual needs, both spiritual and material, to assert oneself in a complex world. Professionalism in pedagogical activity is determined by the level of pedagogical skill. This is also confirmed in the psychological and pedagogical literature. To determine the skill of a teacher, it is very important to find criteria that would help the teacher evaluate his own work, find adequate ways of self-improvement. Usually, pedagogical skill is considered the basis of professionalism - the possession of pedagogical skills and abilities that provide a competent and pedagogically appropriate organization of the pedagogical process.

Conclusion:

A higher level of professionalism is pedagogical skill, we discussed this above. Pedagogical excellence is a complex multidimensional and multicomponent concept, which includes the teacher's ability to influence effectively the mind, will, and feelings of students. It is associated with the personality of the teacher, with a set of qualities that contribute to ensuring a high level of self-organization of professional activity. The limited combination of different approaches to substantiating the composition of pedagogical skills dictates the logic of constructing a model of a teacher's professional competence from the most general to particular skills. What unites these skills is that they are based on the process of transition from the concrete to the abstract, which can take place at the intuitive, empirical and theoretical levels [51, 132]. Bringing skills to the level of theoretical

analysis is one of the most important tasks of preparing teachers for creative activity. Regardless of the level of generalization of the pedagogical task, the complete cycle of its solution is reduced to the triad "think - act - think" and coincides with the components of pedagogical activity and the skills corresponding to them. The model of a teacher's professional competence can be represented as a unity of his theoretical and practical readiness. A.S. Makarenko discussed the relationship between professional competence and pedagogical skills. Rejecting the statements about the predetermination of pedagogical skill by innate features, inclinations, he showed its conditionality by the level of professional competence. Pedagogical excellence, based on skills, on qualifications, in his opinion, is knowledge of the pedagogical process, the ability to build it, set it in motion [54, 33]. Quite often, pedagogical skill is reduced to the skills and habits of pedagogical technique, while this is only one of the outwardly manifested components of mastery. The special knowledge necessary for mastering pedagogical skills includes, knowledge of pedagogical theory, patterns and principles of education and training, methods and techniques, ways and means of the most effective impact on human consciousness. In professional activities, the teacher relies on the potential of his personality, and the improvement of the general culture allows him to develop professional stability.

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